

Crystallographic, Electrical and Dielectric Studies of Betafite and Calcium Substituted Products

V. S. DARSHANE and V. V. DESHPANDE

Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Institute of Science, Nagpur
and

Department of Chemistry, Rajaram College, Kolhapur

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X-ray investigation of betafite mineral was carried out by introducing Ca^{2+} ions in betafite lattice. On incorporation of 9% Ca^{2+} ions only a single cubic phase was observed. On further increasing the proportion of calcium, another perovskite phase was observed along with pyrochlore. The d.c. resistivity of the various calcium substituted products showed that resistivity decreases sharply during transition from two phase to single phase region. The dielectric measurements at 10^3 c/sec. have been reported. It shows parabolic behaviour with composition.

BETAHITE is a metamict mineral which always contains 15 or more percentage of uranium (as U_3O_8 or UO_3). From the chemical analysis of a large number of samples of Canadian origin, Hogarth¹ has suggested a general formula $A_{16-x}B_{16}(O, OH)_{48}(F, OH)_8$ for pyrochlore-betafite series with x representing vacant sites in the unit cell. The analysis of a natural betafite mineral carried out in the laboratory showed 19% as U_3O_8 . Synthetic betafite was prepared by incorporating 15% of U_3O_8 in $Y_2Ti_2O_7$ (pyrochlore). The pattern showed similarity with natural Madagascar betafite². The synthetic sample consists of pyrochlore as a major phase and brannerite as a minor one. The X-ray, electrical and dielectric properties of calcium substituted betafite products have been reported.

Experimental

The samples were prepared in acetone by mixing component oxides of A.R. quality in appropriate proportions. The pellets were prepared by compressing the powder to 10,000 p.s.i. using polyvinyl acetate as binder. The pellets were first fired at 900° for 20 hr. and then at 1350° for 5 hr in vacuum.

The X-ray diffractometer patterns were taken on Philips machine using $Cu K\alpha$ radiation with nickel filter.

The d.c. resistivity was measured on Multi-megohm meter (Type MOM 11, Wissenschaftlich-Technische Werkstatte GmbH, Weilheim/obb, made in Germany) at various temperatures. A "pye" type portable potentiometer was used to measure the thermocouple E.M.F. The end faces of each pellet were coated with a thin layer of conducting colloidal silver paste (A.R. Grade). The sample holder for resistivity measurement was made up of silica tube. The whole assembly was heated in a Kanthal-wound tube furnace at a constant heating rate.

In order to measure the capacity of a parallel plate condenser, made up of the pellet, Marconi LCR bridge was used.

Results and Discussion

The results of X-ray, electrical and dielectric properties of betafite and calcium substituted products are given in Table 1.

From Table 1, it is observed that on introducing 3% Ca^{2+} ions in betafite, intensity of the brannerite phase decreased and the lattice constant of the pyrochlore phase increased to 10.037 Å. When 9% of Ca^{2+} ions were incorporated, a solid solution between pyrochlore and brannerite phases was obtained and only a single cubic phase was observed³. On further increasing the proportion of calcium, another perovskite phase was observed along with pyrochlore.

In the compositions A to E (Table 1), the Wilson's Law

$$\rho = \rho_0 \text{Exp}(\Delta E/KT)$$

is obeyed in the temperature ranges as follows :-

- A — 410 to 544 °K
- B — 300 to 589 °K
- C — 405 to 642 °K
- D — 450 to 610 °K
- E — 425 to 598 °K

The activation energy is calculated only for the slopes where Wilson's Law is obeyed.

The plot of $\log \rho$ vs. reciprocal of absolute temperature for various substitutions of calcium in betafite is shown in Fig. 1. From Fig. 1, the values of activation energies (eV) are calculated.

TABLE I. SUBSTITUTION OF CALCIUM OXIDE IN BETAFITE

S.No.	Composition (Wt.%)				Phases present	Activation energy (ev)	Dielectric constant at 10^3 c/sec.
	Y ₂ O ₃	CaO	U ₃ O ₈	TiO ₂			
A	43.56	—	15	41.44	Betafite (pyrochlore, $a = 10.02$) + UTi ₂ O ₆ ($a = 9.89, b = 3.73$ and $c = 6.97$ Å, $\beta = 118.58^\circ$)	0.5704	108.80
B	40.56	3	15	41.44	Betafite(pyrochlore $a = 10.037$) + UTi ₂ O ₆ (trace)	0.6449	82.25
C	34.56	9	15	41.44	Pyrochlore ($a = 10.051$ Å)	0.6200	80.70
D	28.56	15	15	41.44	Pyrochlore ($a = 10.091$ Å) + Perovskite (trace)	0.9922	135.80
E	22.56	21	15	41.44	Pyrochlore ($a = 10.091$ Å) + Perovskite ($a = 7.595$ Å).	0.7440	146.56

Fig. 1. Resistivity as a function of temperature and calcium oxide concentration in betafite.

From Fig. 1, it is observed that resistivity increases with increase in calcium content, except at 9% of calcium oxide, where a single phase has been observed.

The sharp decrease in resistivity may be due to absence of brannerite phase and formation of a solid solution (continuous matrix) between pyrochlore and mono-

clinic phases and then after sharp decrease in resistivity, resistivity increases with increase in calcium content.

phase region may be attributed to the change from two phase (lower symmetry) region to single phase (high symmetry) region.

Fig. 2. Dielectric constant as a function of calcium oxide concentration in betafite.

The above results are quite in agreement with the results of Tien⁴ on the system ZrO_2 - $CaZrO_3$ and Johansen and Cleary⁵ on the system CaO - ZrO_2 .

From Fig. 1, it is observed that activation energy values in the low temperature range are lower than in high temperature range. The lower values of activation energies may be due to non-stoichiometry in the surface leading to oxidation vacancies and surface states.

The plot of dielectric constant as a function of composition is given in Fig. 2. It shows a parabolic behaviour with composition. It is observed that similar to the resistivity variations, a minimum value of dielectric constant (30.7 at 10^3 c/sec.) is observed in the single cubic phase region. One of the factors which affect dielectric constant is crystal symmetry. The minimum value of dielectric constant in single

A similar type of variation has been reported while studying dielectric properties of the system $BaTiO_3$ - $BaUO_3$ by VanLoan and Chakrabarty⁶.

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